

YUQORI TARTIBLI TAQSIMLANGAN PARAMETRLI BOSHQARUV

MASALASINI CHEKLI AYIRMALI USUL BILAN YECHISH

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Annotatsiya: Keltirilgan maqolada yuqori tartibli taqsimlangan parametrli boshqaruv masalasini chekli ayirmali usullar bilan yechish ko'rib chiqilgan. Maqolada masalaning qo'yilishi, issiqlik almashish turlari, birjinsli sterjenda issiqlik tarqalish jarayoni qonunlari, boshlang'ich, chegaraviy shartlarni qo'yilishi, yuqori tartibli taqsimlangan parametrli boshqaruv masalasini chekli ayirmali usul bilan yechish va asosiy tushuncha, ta'rif va toeramalar ketma-ketligi batafsil keltirib o'tilgan.

Аннотация: В цитируемой статье рассматривается решение задачи управления распределенными параметрами высокого порядка методами конечных разностей. В статье представлены задачи, виды теплообмена, закономерности процесса теплоотвода в однородном потоке, задание начальных и граничных условий, решение задачи управления распределенными параметрами высокого порядка методом конечных разностей, а также основные понятия, определение и последовательность посылок.

Summary: The solution of the high-order distributed parameter control problem by finite difference methods is considered in the cited article. The article presents the problem, types of heat exchange, the laws of the heat dissipation process in a homogeneous stream, setting the initial and boundary conditions, solving the high-order distributed parameter control problem by the finite difference method, and the basic concept, definition and sequence of premises. cited in detail.

Kalit so'zlar: Parabolik tenglama, differensial, parallelepiped, tugunlar, silindir, sirt, diagonal, approksimatsiya, terminal to'plam, ortogonal, vector, matrisa, qatlam.

Ключевые слова: Параболическое уравнение, дифференциал, параллелепипед, узлы, цилиндр, поверхность, диагональ, аппроксимация, терминальное множество, ортогональный, вектор, матрица, слой.

Keywords: Parabolic equation, differential, parallelepiped, nodes, cylinder, surface, diagonal, approximation, terminal set, orthogonal, vector, matrix, layer.

Quyidagi parabolik tenglama bilan berilgan, taqsimlangan boshqariluvchi sistemani qaraymiz,

$$z_t + Az = -u + v, \quad z|_{t=0} = f(x), \quad z|_{S_T} = 0, \quad (1)$$

bu yerda $z = z(x, t)$ – noma'lum funksiya $x = (x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n) \in \Omega \subset R^n, n \geq 1$, $\Omega = \{x \in R^n : 0 \leq x_1 \leq 1, 0 \leq x_2 \leq 1, \dots, 0 \leq x_n \leq 1\}$ - koordinata tekisliklariga parallel bo'lgan qirralarga ega n -o'lchovli kub, $t \in [0, T], T$ – ixtiyoriy musbat konstanta;

$$Az = -\sum_{\alpha=1}^n \frac{\partial}{\partial x_\alpha} (a_\alpha(x) \frac{\partial z}{\partial x_\alpha}),$$

$a_\alpha(x) - x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n$ bo'yicha uzluksiz differensiallanuvchi Ω dagi funksiya.

Faraz qilaylik shunday $\nu > 0$ haqiqiy son mavjudki, ixtiyoriy $x \in \Omega$ uchun $a_\alpha(x) \geq \nu, \alpha = 1, 2, \dots, n$ tengsizliklar bajarilsin, $u, v - L_2(Q_T)$ sinfdan olingan boshqaruv funksiyalari bo'lib, $Q_T = \{(x, t) | x \in \Omega, t \in (0, T]\} - R^{n+1}$ dagi ochiq silindir; $f \in L_2(\Omega), S_T = \{(x, t) | x \in \partial\Omega, t \in (0, T]\} - Q_T$ silindirning yon sirti, $\partial\Omega - \Omega$ sohaning chegarasi. $u = u(x, t)$ – funksiya bilan birinchi o'yinchi (quvuvchi) boshqaradi, $v = v(x, t)$ – funksiya bilan ikkinchi (qochuvchi) o'yinchi boshqaradi, $u(x, t) \in \bar{P}, v(x, t) \in \bar{Q}, \bar{P}$ va $\bar{Q} - R^1$ dagi bo'sh bo'lmagan kompaktlar [1].

(1) masalaning sonli yechimi uchun qo'llaniladigan metod chekli ayirmalar metodi hisoblanadi [2].

R^{n+1} Evklid fazosini (x, t) o'zgaruvchilar $x_{i_\alpha} = i_\alpha h, h = \frac{1}{r}, i = 0, \pm 1, \dots,$ va $t_k = k l, l = \frac{T}{\theta}, k = 0, 1, 2, \dots$ tekisliklar bilan $Q_{(i_\alpha, k)} = \omega_{(hl)} \times (kl, (k+1)l) = \{(x, t) : i_\alpha h < x_{i_\alpha} < (i_\alpha + 1)h, kl < t < (k+1)l\}$ parallelopipedlarga bo'lamiz. Bu yerda r, θ – biror natural sonlardir. Q_T to'plamga tegishli (x_i, t_k) nuqtalar Q_{Thl} to'rni hosil qiladi va uning tugunlari bo'ladi. Har bir tugunda qo'shni tugunlar mavjud. Agar barcha qo'shni tugunlar ham Q_{Thl} ga tegishli bo'lsa, u holda $(x_i, t_k) = (i_1 h, i_2 h, \dots, i_n h, kl)$ tugun "ichki" aks holda (x_i, t_k) tugun "chegaraviy" deb ataladi.

(1) tenglamaning approksimatsiyasi sifatida quyidagi to'rli tenglamani qabul qilamiz:

$$\frac{z_{i,k+1} - z_{i,k}}{l} = \frac{1}{h^2} \sum_{\alpha=1}^n \left[a_{\alpha, (i_{\alpha} - \frac{1}{2})} z_{i_{\alpha}-1,k} - \left(a_{\alpha, (i_{\alpha} - \frac{1}{2})} + a_{\alpha, (i_{\alpha} + \frac{1}{2})} \right) z_{i,k} + a_{\alpha, (i_{\alpha} + \frac{1}{2})} z_{i_{\alpha}+1,k} \right] - u_{i,k} + v_{i,k} \quad (2)$$

Bu yerda h va l mos ravishda x va t bo'yicha qadamlar qiymati, $i_{\alpha} = 1, 2, \dots, r-1$, $\alpha = 1, 2, \dots, n$, $k = 0, 1, \dots, \theta-1$,

$$z_{i,k} = z_{i_1, i_2, \dots, i_n, k} = z(i_1 h, i_2 h, \dots, i_n h, kl),$$

$$z_{i_{\alpha}-1,k} = z(i_1 h, i_2 h, \dots, i_{\alpha-1} h, (i_{\alpha} - 1)h, i_{\alpha+1} h, \dots, i_n h, kl),$$

$$z_{i_{\alpha}+1,k} = z(i_1 h, i_2 h, \dots, i_{\alpha-1} h, (i_{\alpha} + 1)h, i_{\alpha+1} h, \dots, i_n h, kl),$$

$$u_{i,k} = u(i_1 h, i_2 h, \dots, i_n h, kl), \quad v_{i,k} = v(i_1 h, i_2 h, \dots, i_n h, kl),$$

$$a_{\alpha, (i_{\alpha} - \frac{1}{2})} = a_{\alpha} (i_1 h, i_2 h, \dots, i_{\alpha-1} h, (i_{\alpha} - \frac{1}{2})h, i_{\alpha+1} h, \dots, i_n h),$$

$$a_{\alpha, (i_{\alpha} + \frac{1}{2})} = a_{\alpha} (i_1 h, i_2 h, \dots, i_{\alpha-1} h, (i_{\alpha} + \frac{1}{2})h, i_{\alpha+1} h, \dots, i_n h).$$

Chegaraviy shartlarni yozamiz $z|_{t=0} = f(x)$ shartni $z_{i,0} = z(i_1 h, i_2 h, \dots, i_n h)$, $i_{\alpha} = 1, 2, \dots, r-1$, $\alpha = 1, 2, \dots, n$ shart bilan almashtirish mumkin. Xuddi shu kabi, chegaraviy tugun nuqtalar $(i_1 h, i_2 h, \dots, i_n h, kl)$ uchun $z|_{S_T} = 0$ shartni $z_{i,k} = z_{i_1, i_2, \dots, i_n, k} = 0$, $i_{\alpha} = 0, r$, $\alpha = 1, 2, \dots, n$, $k = 0, 1, \dots, \theta$ shart bilan almashtirish mumkin.

Agar (2) to'rtli tenglama turg'un bo'lib, (1) tenglamani approksimatsiyalasa, u holda (2) tenglamaning $z_{i,k}$ yechimi (1) masalaning z yechimiga yaqinlashadi va quyidagi tengsizlik o'rinli bo'ladi:

$$\|(z)_{hl} - z_{i,k}\|_{\Phi_{hl}} \leq K_1 l + K_2 h^2 \quad (3)$$

bu yerda $(z)_{hl}$ – (1) tenglama z yechimining to'rt tugun nuqtalaridagi aniq qiymati, $z_{i,k}$ – (2) tenglamaning yechimi, $K_1, K_2 = const$.

Endi qulaylik uchun (2) masalani matrisa ko'rinishida yozamiz.

$$z_{k+1} = Cz_k - lu_k + lv_k, \quad k = 0, 1, 2, \dots, \theta-1, \quad z_0 = \bar{f}, \quad (4)$$

z_k, u_k, v_k – H – o'lchovli vektorlar. Bu yerda H $t = kl$ qatlamdagi ichki tugun nuqtalar soni, $H = (r-1)^n$.

$$z_k = (z_{1,1,\dots,1,k}, z_{1,1,\dots,2,k}, \dots, z_{1,1,\dots,r-1,k}, \dots, z_{i_1, i_2, \dots, i_n, k}, \dots, z_{r-1, r-1, \dots, r-1, k})^T,$$

$$u_k = (u_{1,1,\dots,1,k}, u_{1,1,\dots,2,k}, \dots, u_{1,1,\dots,r-1,k}, \dots, u_{i_1, i_2, \dots, i_n, k}, \dots, u_{r-1, r-1, \dots, r-1, k})^T,$$

$$v_k = (v_{1,1,\dots,1,k}, v_{1,1,\dots,2,k}, \dots, v_{1,1,\dots,r-1,k}, \dots, v_{i_1,i_2,\dots,i_n,k}, \dots, v_{r-1,r-1,\dots,r-1,k})^T,$$

mos holda,

$$\bar{f} = (f(h, h, \dots, h), f(h, h, \dots, 2h), \dots, f(h, h, \dots, (r-1)h), \dots, \\ \dots, f(i_1 h, i_2 h, \dots, i_n h), \dots, f((r-1)h, (r-1)h, \dots, (r-1)h))^T -$$

boshlang'ich vektor, $C - H - o'lchovli$ quyidagi ko'rinishdagi uch diagonalli kvadrat matrisa:

$$C = \begin{pmatrix} c & \bar{c} & 0 & 0 & 0 & \dots & 0 \\ \underline{c} & c & \bar{c} & 0 & 0 & \dots & 0 \\ 0 & \underline{c} & c & \bar{c} & 0 & \dots & 0 \\ \dots & \dots & \dots & \dots & \dots & \dots & \dots \\ 0 & \dots & 0 & \underline{c} & c & \bar{c} & 0 \\ 0 & \dots & 0 & 0 & \underline{c} & c & \bar{c} \\ 0 & \dots & 0 & 0 & 0 & \underline{c} & c \end{pmatrix},$$

bu yerda $\underline{c} = \frac{l}{h^2} \sum_{\alpha=1}^n a_{\alpha, (i_\alpha - \frac{1}{2})}$; $c = 1 - \frac{l}{h^2} \sum_{\alpha=1}^n \left(a_{\alpha, (i_\alpha - \frac{1}{2})} + a_{\alpha, (i_\alpha + \frac{1}{2})} \right)$; $\bar{c} = \frac{l}{h^2} \sum_{\alpha=1}^n a_{\alpha, (i_\alpha + \frac{1}{2})}$.

R^H da M terminal to'plam berilgan bo'lsin.

2-Ta'rif. (1.19) o'yinda $z_0 = \bar{f} \in R^H \setminus M$ nuqtadan quvishni $N \leq \theta$ qadamda tugatish mumkin deyiladi, agar ixtiyoriy $\bar{v}_0, \bar{v}_1, \dots, \bar{v}_{N-1}$ qochuvchining boshqaruvi uchun quvuvchining shunday $\bar{u}_0, \bar{u}_1, \dots, \bar{u}_{N-1}$ boshqaruvini qurish mumkun bo'lsaki, natijada (1.19) tenglamaning ushbu boshqaruvlarga mos $(z_0, \bar{z}_1, \dots, \bar{z}_N)$ yechimi uchun qandaydir $d \leq N$ da $\bar{z}_d \in M$ shart bajarilsa.

Aytaylik (4) o'yinda terminal to'plam $M = M_0 + M_1$ ko'rinishga ega, bu yerda $M_0 - (H - \gamma) - o'lchovli$ R^H ning chiziqli qism fazosi, $M_1 - L$ ning to'plam ostisi $L \times M_0 = R^H$. Endi Π orqali R^H dan L ga ortogonal akslantirish operatori matrisasini belgilaymiz. $A + B$ va $A * B$ orqali esa A, B to'plamlarning algebraik yig'indisi va geometrik ayirmasini belgilaymiz.

$$P = \underbrace{\bar{P} \times \bar{P} \times \dots \times \bar{P}}_H, \quad Q = \underbrace{\bar{Q} \times \bar{Q} \times \dots \times \bar{Q}}_H, \quad M_1 = \underbrace{\bar{M}_1 \times \bar{M}_1 \times \dots \times \bar{M}_1}_\gamma,$$

$$1 \leq \gamma \leq H, \quad W(0) = W\{0\},$$

$$W(m) = \sum_{k=0}^{m-1} [\Pi C^k l P^* \Pi C^k l Q], W_1(m) = M_1 + W(m) \quad \text{bu yerda } m = 1, 2, \dots, \theta.$$

[1,2] ishlarda (1) o'yinni yechish uchun quyidagi yetarli shartlar olingan.

Teorema 1.1. Aytaylik, N har bir $\Pi C^m z_0 \in W_1(m)$ uchun o'rinli bo'lgan, m natural sonlardan eng kichiki bo'lsin. U holda $z_0 = \bar{f}$ nuqtadan quvishni N qadamda tugatish mumkin.

Teorema 1.2. Agar N har bir $\Pi C^m z_0 \in W_2(m)$ uchun o'rinli bo'lgan, m natural sonlardan eng kichiki bo'lsa, u holda z_0 nuqtadan quvishni N qadamda tugatish mumkin.

Teorema 1.3. Agar M_1 - qavariq to'plam va N har bir

$$\Pi C^m z_0 \in W_3(m) \quad (5)$$

uchun o'rinli bo'lgan, m natural sonlardan eng kichiki bo'lsa, u holda z_0 nuqtadan quvishni N qadamda tugatish mumkin.

Teorema 1.4. (3) tengsizlikda $a \neq \frac{1}{2}$ bo'lsa, $K_1 l + K_2 h^2 < \varepsilon$ va $a = \frac{1}{2}$ bo'lsa, $\bar{K}_1 l^2 + \bar{K}_2 h^2 < \varepsilon$ o'rinli bo'lsin va (4) o'yinda $z_0 = \bar{f}$ nuqtadan 2-ta'rifga ko'ra quvishni tugatish mumkin. U holda, (1) o'yinda $z|_{t=0} = z(x,0) = f(x)$ boshlang'ich holatdan 1-ta'rifga ko'ra quvishni tugatish mumkin.

Xulosa o'rnida shuni aytish kerakki, masalaning qo'yilishi, issiqlik almashish turlari, birjinsli sterjenda issiqlik tarqalish jarayoni qonunlari, boshlang'ich, chegaraviy shartlarni qo'yilishi, yuqori tartibli taqsimlangan parametrli boshqaruv masalasini chekli ayirmali usul bilan yechish va asosiy tushuncha, ta'rif va toeramalar kelgusi ishlarimizda natijalarni olishga samarali hissa qo'shadi degan umiddaman.

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